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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CNR	Italian National Research Council
CMS	Content Management System
CVS	Code Versioning System
CWP	Coordinating Working Party on Fishery Statistics
DD&AS	Data Discovery & Access Service
DIVAnd	Data-Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions
D4Science	Data Infrastructure promoting Open Science (managed by CNR)
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FIRMS	Fisheries and Resources Monitoring System
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
GUIS	Graphical User Interface
JSON	Javascript Object Notation

IDE	Integrated Development Environment
MFS	Mediterranean Forecasting System (MFS)
MHW	Marine HeatWave
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisations
RIA	Rich Internet Application
SSC	Sea Surface Currents
SPARQL	Standard query language and protocol for Linked Open Data on the web or for RDF triplestores
TBD	To Be Defined
TBA	To Be Arranged
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

Keywords

EOSC; Virtual Labs; Big Data; Virtual Research Environment; Data infrastructures

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

User feedback collected across hackathons, consultation surveys, webinars, and an open survey between January 2025 (first beta release of the VLabs) and June 2026 (report delivery) reflects a broadly positive reception of the Blue-Cloud 2026 VLabs, while providing a consistent set of actionable recommendations for improvement.

Across all five VLabs, accessibility and ease of navigation were rated positively by the large majority of participants. The platform was widely recognised for the value it delivers to marine research communities, bringing together ready-to-use datasets, pre-configured environments, and integrated analytical tools in ways that save researchers significant time. Scientific relevance was consistently affirmed: individual VLabs were identified as directly applicable to research on coastal ocean dynamics, fisheries monitoring, carbon-plankton modelling, marine environmental indicators, and climate change impact assessment, including their potential contribution to Digital Twin Ocean capabilities. Several VLabs were also highlighted as valuable for teaching and capacity building.

Recurring technical limitations centred on resource intensity, with users experiencing latency during job execution and storage-related errors preventing the re-running of certain notebooks. Collaborative features and workspace management might require attention, particularly around joint access to VLabs and file transfer performance.

Documentation was generally well regarded, supported by the VLab handbooks and Ocean Teacher Global Academy courses, though users requested more granular guidance at the individual VLab level during hackathon and dedicated troubleshooting resources. Notebook-level improvements were also requested, including better error handling, additional inline comments, and greater flexibility for advanced users to adapt workflows to their own case studies.

All feedback raised at the individual VLab level was addressed by the respective development teams and the corresponding improvements have been implemented in the latest release of the VLabs, published in January 2026. Taken together, the feedback and responses confirm that the VLabs infrastructure delivers strong scientific and operational value, and that the iterative development process has meaningfully enhanced the user experience across the platform.

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1. Introduction

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project has delivered a suite of five Virtual Laboratories (VLabs) designed to advance open, FAIR-compliant marine science across Europe and beyond. Built on the [D4Science infrastructure](#) within the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE), these VLabs bring together diverse ocean datasets, analytical tools, and modelling capabilities into accessible, cloud-based platforms that serve researchers, educators, policymakers, and decision-makers alike.

This document presents the final results of the VLabs developed under the project, encompassing their scientific scope, technical implementation, and the feedback gathered from the user community since their first release in January 2025. It covers five thematic areas: coastal ocean observation integration (VLab 1), coastal current mapping (VLab 2), carbon-plankton dynamics (VLab 3), marine environmental indicators (VLab 4), and global fisheries data (VLab 5). For each VLab, the document describes the services offered, the teams that created them, the feedback received and the practical applications that have already emerged across research, education, and policy contexts.

Alongside the VLabs themselves, the project has invested in capacity building through dedicated Ocean Teacher Global Academy courses, user handbooks, hackathons, webinars, and consultation surveys, ensuring that the tools developed reach and genuinely serve their intended communities. The feedback collected through these activities has been instrumental in iteratively improving the platforms and shaping this final deliverable.

2. VLabs results

This section introduces each Virtual Laboratory (VLab) developed as an outcome of the project. After a brief introduction, the main achievements of each VLab are presented, together with an acknowledgement of the partners involved. All VLabs are hosted on D4Science within the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE).

During the scope of the project, two VLabs users handbooks have been released, one for the beta version released in January 2025 (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14982484>), another version was released in January 2026 (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18714259>) along with the latest version of the VLabs. All additional information regarding data sources, how-to use the VLab and using other data sources can be found in the [handbook](#).

The VLabs can be accessed from the links below:

- [VLab #1: Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations Along Europe \(ICOOE\)](#)
- [VLab #2: Coastal Currents from Observation](#)
- [VLab #3: Carbon Plankton Dynamics](#)
- [VLab #4: Marine Environmental Indicators](#)
- [VLab #5: Global Fisheries Atlas](#)

To be able to access Blue-Cloud 2026 services, users first need to register to the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform by creating an account on the [Blue-Cloud 2026 Gateway](#). The steps are explained in the first section of the [handbook](#).

Figure 1. Blue-Cloud Gateway

For each VLab, a dedicated Ocean Teacher Global Academy self-paced course has been developed to help users adequately use the VLabs.

Figure 2. Ocean Teacher Global Academy course entry point

The courses links can be found below:

- How to use a Virtual Laboratory on ICOOE (Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe) - to be released in Summer 2026
- [How to use a Virtual Laboratory on Coastal Currents from Observation](#)
- [How to use a Virtual Laboratory on Carbon Plankton Dynamics](#)
- How to use a Virtual Laboratory on Marine Environmental Indicators (to be released in Summer 2026)
- [Navigating the Global Fisheries Atlas Virtual Laboratory: Tools & Techniques](#)

Below you will find a summary of each VLab and what they include and offer as services.

2.1. VLab 1: “Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe”

The **Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe (ICOoE)** VLab provides a platform for accessing, integrating, and analysing coastal ocean observations across Europe. It focuses on data collected by the Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories (JERICO-RI) and other European Blue Data Infrastructures, facilitating the study of coastal processes such as biological connectivity, contaminant dispersion, and the effects of river outflows.

The Virtual Lab offers tools for advanced data exploration, including statistical analyses, correlation assessments, and interactive visualisations. These capabilities support the examination of coastal impacts from major storms and the evaluation of repeated glider sections, enhancing the understanding of coastal dynamics.

By integrating diverse datasets and providing analytical tools, the ICOoE Virtual Lab aids researchers in developing informed strategies for coastal management and conservation. Its functionalities are designed to support the creation of FAIR data products, promoting open science practices in marine research.

VLab 1 supports the coastal ocean users through three Thematic Services:

- **Thematic Service 1**, addressing “**Transboundary processes and connectivity along the European margins**”, aims to support user interest in processes such as biological connectivity, contaminants spread, and impacts of river outflows along margins.
- **Thematic Service 2**, “**Extreme Events**”, focusing on coastal impacts of major storms.
- **Thematic Service 3**, “**Ocean glider**” shows the added value of repeated glider sections.

This VLab was created by João Vitorino, [Vânia Lima \(Instituto Hidrográfico\)](#), [Juan Gabriel Fernández, Enrique Castrillo, Nikolaos D. Zarokanellos, Mélanie Juza, Miguel Charcos-Lloréns, Emma Reyes \(SOCIB\)](#) and Jay Pearlman, Rene Garelo, [Sigmund Kluckner \(IEEE France Section\)](#).

The VLab is available [at this link](#).

2.1.1. TS#1: Transboundary processes and connectivity along the European margins

The Thematic Service #1 (TS#1) aims to provide a variety of tools that can support users in working with the observations and complementary information available for a given coastal ocean area, extracting information on transboundary transport and connectivity processes.

Concretely, TS#1 includes:

- A dashboard environment (ShinyProxy app) in the Blue Cloud VRE enabling users’ interface for selection of geographical area, time periods and variable of interest and options for exploration and integration. The thematic service is available for the Iberian Margin global area, although extension to a more general area is possible in the future.
- A preliminary report of available datasets in the Blue Cloud VRE for users’ request providing information about spatial and temporal coverage.

2.1.2. TS#2: Extreme Events

The Thematic Service #2 (TS#2) provides users with access to a portfolio of tools aimed to support the research on and understanding of the impacts of extreme events on the coastal ocean regions of Europe. The designation of “extreme event” comprises a broad range of phenomena that are rare, highly energetic, and often short-lived, and that show a significant deviation from the normal (statistical) conditions. They comprise, among others, extreme storms (*e.g.* hurricanes) promoting energetic waves and important storm surge phenomena, marine heat waves, extreme salinity events, ocean acidification episodes or coastal flooding. The demonstrator case in the Blue Cloud VRE focuses on extreme storm events.

Concretely, TS#2 includes:

- A user interface structure (Dashboard environment, ShinyProxy app) of the Thematic Service, similar to the structure implemented for TS#1 and enabling users' interface for selection of geographical area, extreme event and analysis option. The thematic service is available for the Iberian Margin global area.

Figure 4. The dashboard environment from where users can access TS#2 functionalities.

Figure 5. Example of the graphical outputs of results from the analysis products offered by TS#2, from left to right, characterisation of wave and current conditions during extreme storms, correspondent wave impacts on the seafloor, potential for sediment remobilisation and profiles of waves motions and currents in the water column.

- Datasets corresponding to each one of the 3 storm periods available for this thematic service, comprising EMODnet bathymetry (DTM2024), EMODnet geology seafloor substrate (based on the Folk7 classification), hourly high resolution wave parameters from WFWAM model provided by Copernicus Marine Service, and hourly barotropic currents from NEMO model provided by Copernicus Marine Service.
- Two analysis tools offered to users, the first one aimed to estimate impacts on the bottom sedimentary cover promoted by the conditions associated with the storms (waves and currents), and the second one aimed to estimate how these conditions impact the water column.

2.1.3. TS#3: Ocean glider

Thematic Service #3 (TS#3) is a toolbox for the computation and visualization of physical variables from gliders, as well as derived variables that are relevant for both science and society.

Concretely, TS#3 includes:

- A software library (glider_converter) to produce OG 1.0 NetCDF files from Slocum's raw data. The library is a Python 3 package included in the JupyterHub custom docker image that can be launched from the Virtual Lab.
- A software library (glider_postproc) to produce the advanced data product from a given glider mission dataset: a set of static images and a netCDF gridded dataset (an L2 dataset as defined in the advanced data product manual). In particular, it produces interpolated data on a regular grid (vertical section interpolated across a standard line defined by the user) for potential temperature, salinity, density and geostrophy velocity. The methodology from Juza et al. (2025) has been applied and implemented to compute geostrophic velocities derived from the hydrographic profiles. The implementation process consisted of migrating the original toolbox written in Matlab, to Python 3. The JupyterHub custom image also includes the related Python package.
- A web viewer component hosted by SOCIB as part of its Viewer System.
- Adaptation of the glider_postproc Python package to allow users to process glider missions worldwide, building on the original MATLAB toolbox, which was tailored to the Ibiza Channel use case.

Figure 6. Thematic Service #3 workflow and functionalities.

2.2. VLab 2: “Coastal Currents from Observations”

The **Coastal Currents from Observations VLab** enables users to generate integrated ocean surface current maps by merging data from multiple sources. It uses direct and indirect current measurements, including High Frequency (HF) radar, drifter observations, and geostrophic currents derived from satellite altimetry. The integration relies on the DIVAnd (Data Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions) method, which applies physical constraints such as coastline boundaries, horizontal divergence, and momentum balance to improve the reliability of the output.

This VLab was created by [Abel Dechenne](#), [Alexander Barth](#) (Université de Liège) and [Igor Ruiz Atake](#) (CMCC Foundation - Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate).

The main feature of the VLab is a customisable service delivered through Jupyter notebooks. Users can select a coastal region—depending on data availability and the extent of HF radar coverage, typically ranging from 50 to 200 km offshore—and produce gridded surface current maps in NetCDF format. These maps support Lagrangian simulations, allowing the visualisation of artificial drifter trajectories from user-defined release points. The output also serves as input for the [MEDSLIK-II oil spill model](#), which will be deployed in a Docker container to simulate pollutant dispersion scenarios.

The VLab is available [at this link](#).

Concretely, VLab 2 includes:

- A collection of sea surface currents from drifters and high frequency radar. Conversion of surface elevation (altimetry) onto geostrophic currents.
- Data sources integration onto a regular grid to use DIVAnd interpolation.
- Dataset interpolation following interpolation rules and fundamental hydrodynamical principles.
- Hyperparameter optimization to seek for the reconstruction with the lowest error compared to in-situ observations. This step tunes how far an observation can be interpolated and to which extent a type of dataset is reliable.
- Cross validation based on in-situ observations, coming from independent (not considered for the interpolation) drifter datasets, which also guided the optimization of the hyperparameter.
- Comparison of the interpolation (DIVAnd) results with a geostrophic product from DUACS. The same validation scheme was carried : Monthly averages are compared with one month of independent drifters observations. Both validations are compared to highlight the improvement with DIVAnd technique.
- The surface layer of the hydrodynamical model of the Mediterranean Sea was corrected with the results of DIVAnd and a validation against independent drifters was carried out.

- The outputs from DIVAnd then can be used to perform Oil Spill simulations with the front end application WITOIL for Blue Cloud. The application is capable of identifying the areas in which DIVAnd corrected currents and use them as forcing for the oil spill simulation. The results can be observed in the web platform itself.

Figure 7. Witoil for Blue-Cloud application landing page, demonstrating the areas (in blue) in which an user can launch oil spill simulations using DIVAnd currents.

2.3. VLab 3: “Carbon-Plankton Dynamics”

The **Carbon-Plankton Dynamics Virtual Lab** provides a modelling environment to simulate interactions between nutrients, phytoplankton, zooplankton, and detritus in marine ecosystems. At its core is a [Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton-Detritus \(NPZD\)](#) model that runs in both nitrogen and carbon units, enabling consistent tracking of carbon flows through various ecosystem processes.

The VLab is available [at this link](#).

Initially implemented and validated in the southern North Sea, the model has since been applied to the northern Adriatic Sea. This allows users to explore phytoplankton dynamics in different marine settings and examine factors influencing biomass variability.

The system uses environmental input data such as sea surface temperature, salinity, nutrient concentrations (including DIN, PO₄, and SiO₄), and carbon-related variables like atmospheric pCO₂, wind speed, and pH. These inputs inform the model’s representation of primary and secondary productivity, organic matter degradation, and carbon exchanges with the atmosphere and rivers.

This VLab was created by [Steven Pint](#), [Cyrielle Delvenne](#), [Tom Van Engeland](#), [Gert Everaert](#), [Thanos Gkritzalis](#) (Flanders Marine Institute) and [Matteo Bazzaro](#), [Michele Gianì](#), [Gianpiero Cossarini](#) (National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics).

This VLab includes :

- A Jupyter Notebook that provides a step-by-step guide to run the NPZD model with carbon dynamics included. The notebook contains preloaded examples for both the Adriatic Sea and the Belgian part of the North Sea, but it is also compatible with data from other regions.
- An RShiny App that allows users to explore the effects of changing variables interactively.

Figure 8. The initial browser window after starting up the web application with the model demo.

2.4. VLab 4: “Marine Environmental Indicators”

The Marine Environmental Indicators (MEI) VLab enables users to monitor and evaluate the environmental conditions of marine areas, providing essential support for decision-making in ocean management. By integrating multiple data sources, the platform offers a unified data analysis service, facilitating online computation of indicators through Jupyter Notebooks or a dedicated web application. This application leverages the VRE Analytics Engine services to generate indicator outputs. This VLab 4 provides four indicators (OHC, TRIX, MHW, SSI v2) and the web application. A [video tutorial](#) on how to access the VLab and its indicators can be found on the [Blue-Cloud Youtube Channel](#).

This VLab was created by different teams depending on their indicators:

- **Marine Heatwaves (MHW):** [Francesco Palermo](#), [Giovanni Coppini](#), [Emanuela Clementi](#), [Ronan J. McAdam](#), [Megi Hoxhaj](#), [Rafael Gomes de Menezes](#), [Fabrizio Antonio](#), [Oussema Jerfel](#), [Leandro Fernandes Patricio](#), [Massimiliano Drudi](#), [Antonio Mariani](#) (CMCC)
- **Ocean Heat Content (OH):** [Enrico Baglione](#), [Paolo Oliveri](#) and [Simona Simoncelli](#) (INGV)
- **Trophic State Index (TRIX):** [Nydia Catalina Reyes Suarez](#) (ORCID: [0000-0002-3906-471X](#), OGS), [Marina Lipizer](#) (ORCID: [0000-0001-5707-6338](#), OGS), [Alessandro Altenburger](#) (ORCID: [0009-0002-5853-1800](#), OGS), [Nikola Holodkov](#) (ORCID: [0000-0002-3804-2631](#), OGS), [Megan Anne French](#) (ORCID: [0000-0002-5837-1360](#), OGS), [Alessandra Giorgetti](#) (ORCID: [0000-0002-0914-4831](#), OGS)
- **Storm Severity Index (SSI) V2:** [Jan Willem Noteboom](#) (KNMI) . The CCP based implementation by [Marco Lettere](#), Vincenzo Cestone, Mauro Mugnaini (Nubisware S.r.l.).

This VLab includes :

- The “Ocean Heat Content (OHC)” indicator is implemented in a Python Jupyter Notebook (OHC_SEAS_NORM_JSON.ipynb). The current workflow is fully operational and controlled through an external configuration file (config_OHC.json), ensuring high portability. The calculation does not perform spatial interpolation itself, but directly ingests already prepared gridded NetCDF temperature fields (e.g., generated via DIVAnd tool) and their corresponding reference climate normals. The supported observational data sources for generating these gridded fields include CMEMS CORA, EuroArgo/Argo, WOD, SeaDataNet, in line with the physics workbench (T3.2, phy-wb) data plan. Equipped with interactive widgets for flexible spatial and

temporal subsetting, the infrastructure is already fully prepared to use the integrated dataset derived from the physics workbench cleaning procedures as its final input, alongside any other customized gridded fields uploaded to the VLab. The OHC release is based on the deployment of SeaDataCloud set up, but the use of the targeted data sources in progress, following the activities of T3.2 which will allow data access through the query of Beacon monolithic instances.

Figure 9. Screenshot of the OHC notebook running in the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE).

Figure 10. Seasonal OHC anomaly comparison (1981–2010 baseline).

The figure shows seasonal Ocean Heat Content (OHC) anomalies for Winter, Spring, Summer, and Autumn, comparing three datasets (WOD, SeaDataNet, CORA) all referenced to the 1981–2010 climatology. A zero-anomaly dashed line is used as reference. The three products display a coherent multidecadal evolution with a marked increase from the 1990s onward, while inter-dataset differences are more visible in the earlier part of the record and vary by season.

- The eutrophication indicator “**Trophic Index (TRIX)**” produces spatially interpolated TRIX maps and related products for the Mediterranean Sea. Interpolation uses DIVAnd-based routines originally implemented in Python/Jupyter notebooks and recently migrated into a dockerized web application. Data sources for the final release include the 2025 unrestricted profiles and time series from EMODnet Chemistry; these datasets are used to compute interpolated fields and populate the interactive TRIX map.

Key results:

- TRIx interactive map from DIVAnd interpolated gridded DIN, DO, CHL and TP fields from in situ nutrients, oxygen and chlorophyll measurements across the Mediterranean basin.
- Temporal coverage: Two decades are provided: 2003-01-01 to 2012-12-31 and 2013-01-01 to 2023-12-31.
- Validation: Comparisons with independent in situ stations and aggregated EMODnet metrics show good agreement in areas with sufficient sampling; interpolation uncertainty increases in sparsely sampled or highly variable coastal zones. Uncertainty fields are produced alongside TRIx maps to support interpretation.
- Performance and implementation: The web application is a dockerized version of the VLab Python notebook ([TRIX.ipynb](#)) that implements the TRIx methodology of Fiori et al. (2016). The current release visualizes L2 DIVA maps with a relative error threshold of 0.5 for the two decades and allows users to load their own data files. The workflow applies the 12 NM sea boundary from MarineRegions to focus on coastal eutrophication signatures. Users can upload local measurement campaigns to quickly generate TRIx maps and compare local conditions against regional baselines.

a)

b)

Figure 11. TRIX web application. a) Visualization of L2 spring TRIX index for the 2003–2012 decade at 0–5 m depth. b) Example of reusing the tool with the user’s own data.

Applications and users

- Monitoring and reporting: Production TRIX maps support national and regional monitoring programs for eutrophication assessment, trend detection, and reporting under regional conventions and policies.
 - Management and decision support: Coastal managers can use TRIX outputs to identify hotspots, prioritize monitoring, and design mitigation measures (for example, nutrient load reductions). Uncertainty fields help assess confidence in site-level decisions.
 - Research and outreach: The simplified web interface and visual outputs are suitable for scientific exploration, and outreach, enabling stakeholders and students to explore eutrophication patterns and learn indicator interpretation.
-
- The **Marine Heatwaves (MHW)** indicator was developed in Python and Jupyter Notebook using the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) datasets of Mediterranean Satellite operational products and the Mediterranean Forecasting System (MedFS) model as data sources. The tool can produce maps and time series of MHW with the information provided by the user such as date range and geographical region of interest. The MHW implementation consists of two operational notebooks for analysis over the Mediterranean Sea: one extracts and analyzes area-averaged Sea Surface Temperature (SST) time series to detect MHW events over user-defined periods and regions; the other computes spatial maps of SST anomalies and MHW intensity categories for chosen dates. The methodology enables flexible parameter configuration, including temporal windows, geographical regions (predefined masks or custom rectangles), climatology reference periods, and detection thresholds. Outputs are provided as PNG files, interactive HTML visualizations and NetCDF files for further analysis. Notebooks and the associated input/output data are hosted and persist within the VRE, ensuring reproducibility and easy access for users.
 - **Storm Severity Index Version 2 (SSI v2)** calculates maps and time series data to quantify exceptional atmospheric wind circumstances (i.e. storms). Individual storm events and storm seasons of areas can be calculated, classified and compared and long term SSI trends can be calculated to investigate the storm climatology. A generalized version of the Jupyter Notebook has been implemented as a FAIR computational method on the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP).

- The Marine Environmental Indicators (MEI) **Webapp** service provides a web-based graphical interface that enables users to monitor and evaluate environmental conditions of marine areas, offering essential support for decision-making in ocean management. By integrating multiple data sources, the platform offers unified data analysis functionality with online computation of the indicators developed in this VLab. The webapp presents an intuitive interface for indicator-based processing with flexible output options. Users define specific parameters through the interface, and the system handles complex data extraction and transformation automatically. Additional parameters for outputs are dynamically proposed based on the selected indicator. The service provides two core functionalities: generating new outputs starting from available data, and accessing/visualizing previously calculated results. Once submitted, user requests are queued for processing with real-time status tracking until completion. The platform communicates with the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP) service of VLab 4 for managing computational workflows and executing the processing requests generated through the web interface.

2.5. VLab 5: “Global Fisheries Atlas”

The Global Fisheries Atlas VLab acts as an umbrella built on top of authoritative data or knowledge sources describing fisheries activities. This VLab aims to better describe fisheries activities at a global scale either by disseminating knowledge or data. To do so, more than ten sources have been harmonised and are accessible from the Global Fisheries Atlas. The VLab content is made accessible by various entry points either through **graphic user interface (GUI)** or programmatic access depending on users needs and profiles. Users can access or use web mapping products to browse and explore the **Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF)** knowledge base as well as datasets describing Tuna Atlas fisheries at a global scale. Beyond data already integrated, this VLab also provides methods and tools to reproduce, update or customize this work to deal with other use cases. [Online training material](#) has also been prepared with practical exercises to support capacity building and self-paced learning.

VLab 5 was created by [Julien Barde](#), [Bastien Grasset](#) (IRD), [Yannis Marketakis](#) (FORTH) and FAO and tuna RFMOs data managers involved in **FIRMS (IOTC, ICCAT, IATTC, WCPFC, CCSBT)**.

The VLab is available [at this link](#).

Below are listed the services available:

For what regards **GRSF**:

- GRSF Knowledge Base (GRSF KB) undergoes extensive data normalization and merging processes. It aggregates data from multiple diverse and geographically dispersed data sources

(currently four: [Fisheries and Resources Monitoring System \(FIRMS\)](#), [RAM Legacy Stock Assessment Database](#), [FishSource](#), [FAO SDG 14.4.1](#)) into a unified knowledge graph. The content of the GRSF Knowledge Base has been updated four times (01/2024, 09/2024, 03/2025 and 11/2025).

- Data sources contain complementary information (both conceptually and geographically), and all of them contribute to the overall aim of building a comprehensive and transparent global reference set of stocks and fisheries record.
- Data accuracy has been improved by proposing stock merges where appropriate.
- Additional resources (mainly species and water areas) have been integrated from publicly available data sources (such as GBIF, FishBase) to support GRSF standardization.
- GRSF Knowledge Base resources can be accessed through various means: (a) a dedicated catalogue (provided by D4Science infrastructure where the GRSF Administrator can assess, validate, and make data publicly available); (b) a RESTfull API; (c) a public SPARQL endpoint, and others.
- The catalogue, SPARQL endpoint and the API are now directly made available into the VLab 5 with the publication workflow by using more sustainable services (D4Science gcube:grsf-publisher).

For what regards **Global Tuna Atlas**:

- Uses workflows to generate harmonized global datasets from heterogeneous sources and provides visualization tools (*e.g.*, Dashboards or Web mapping powered by Shiny applications).
- Integrates tuna fisheries data from the five tuna RFMOS (Regional Fisheries Management Organizations) providing heterogeneous regional datasets.
- Emphasises on good coding practices and robust data management and sharing approaches.
- Harmonization is performed to ensure compliance with widely used standards: datasets published following OGC standards for spatial metadata, data formats, and access protocols as well as the CWP standards for fisheries data structure.
- All code is openly available on the GitHub organization's repositories: [FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas GitHub](#) (including snapshots of the virtual environments and Docker images ensuring the reproducibility of the code) with some of the main releases of repositories also being assigned a DOI on Zenodo (*e.g.*, the [data generation workflow](#)). All DOIs are available in the VLab.
- RStudio IDE server of the VLab 5 is now configured by default with several pre-loaded GitHub repositories, datafiles and packages (using *renv* package to manage multiple virtual environments and a common cache available for all users) to improve reproducibility and ready to go development environments.

- RShiny apps make use of these different DOIs to access and store directly both the data and code in their containers, in addition to the database connection, which improves the reproducibility.
- Continuous integration pipelines (GitHub actions) have been implemented to automate the containerization process and the deployment of the code in the infrastructure, e.g., visualization applications, such as RShiny apps ([example](#)).
- The main yearly updates of datasets, including FIRMS products, have been assigned new version DOIs (published on Zenodo as part of the Blue-Cloud community), with a yearly update in 2024, 2025 and a last yearly update achieved in may 2026, e.g. [FIRMS datasets](#) and upper levels of processings (e.g. [Level 2](#), the full list of DOIs is available on the VLab homepage)

3. Users Feedback

Since the first release of the V Labs in January 2025, feedback has been gathered from consultation surveys (58 high-level participants, May 2025), hackathons (131 students, researchers and software developers, September 2025), webinars (participants from different background including research, project management, policy, throughout the project) and an open survey (3 researchers and students, opened in February 2026) in each VLab. All feedback has been explained below and is divided into sections. The first section gathers feedback from Blue-Cloud services as a whole. The next five sections are dedicated to each VLab, from VLab 1 to VLab 5.

3.1. General feedback of Blue-Cloud services

Participant feedback from consultation and VLab survey, hackathon and webinars reveals a broadly positive reception of the V Labs, alongside a set of recurring themes that point to clear opportunities for improvement.

In terms of accessibility, the majority of participants found the V Labs straightforward to reach and navigate, with ten out of twelve respondents rating access as easy. The platform was recognised for offering a rich ecosystem of services for marine research, bringing together models, data, and processing capabilities in a way that saves researchers significant time. The availability of ready-to-use datasets and pre-configured environments was highlighted as a key strength, particularly for users with limited coding experience. Training materials and instruction sheets provided by the support team were cited as effective onboarding aids that helped users orient themselves quickly.

Despite this positive baseline, user feedback highlighted specific areas where user onboarding and documentation could be further enhanced to maximise platform utility. Regarding performance, reports

of latency during job execution and workflow interruptions were largely identified as a consequence of misaligned storage tier usage. The platform provides a tiered storage architecture: the Dataspace offers high-performance, low-latency access for data-intensive computation, whereas the Workspace is specifically engineered for provenance, versioning, and secure long-term persistence, which entails overhead that is not suitable for active working folders. Users who adopted these storage tiers according to their intended design reported seamless operations, suggesting that these challenges can be mitigated through targeted training on best practices. Similarly, the perceived absence of a federated data catalogue appears to be a discoverability gap rather than a technical one. The Data Discovery and Access Service (DDAS) already provides comprehensive, cross-environment data integration; however, awareness of this service and its interoperability with specific VLab workflows was inconsistent. Future efforts will therefore focus on strengthening documentation, improving the visibility of the DDAS within the user interface, and providing clearer guidance on storage strategies to ensure all practitioners can fully leverage the platform's capabilities.

Collaborative features were identified as an area requiring attention. Hackathon participants found joint access to V Labs from a shared workspace unintuitive (knowing that they did not have previous experience working in cloud environments and they had to link V Labs features to win the hackathon), and one raised a privacy concern related to user name visibility when inviting collaborators. Several respondents suggested practical interface enhancements, including a dashboard showing active resource usage, the ability to submit jobs without configuring a Jupyter environment, a deploy button within JupyterHub, and the option to install custom environments to improve interoperability and keep libraries current.

Documentation was generally well regarded, though participants requested more granular guidance at the individual VLab level, including separate PDF documentation per VLab, a summary table describing each VLab's objectives, input data, outputs, and spatial coverage, and a known-issues page paired with more detailed troubleshooting resources. Additional inline code comments within notebooks were also requested to improve interpretability.

Looking ahead, participants expressed interest in coupling the platform with high-performance computing resources to support regional model execution, in alignment with digital twin use cases. The overall assessment confirms that the V Labs infrastructure provides strong foundational value and that targeted improvements to documentation, data discoverability, collaborative tooling, and resource transparency would substantially enhance the user experience.

3.2. VLab 1 “Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe” Feedback

3.2.1. Thematic Service #1: Transboundary Transport & Connectivity

Positive feedback was received from users, who highlighted that the VLab effectively supported their research activities. Users noted that both the VLab and Thematic Service 1 were easy to access and appreciated the clear guidance provided in the “How-to” section, particularly on how to retrieve and use the data.

They also emphasised that selecting the area of interest and time period was simple, intuitive, and straightforward, making the service accessible to users with different levels of technical expertise.

In addition to this positive feedback, users suggested that the VLab could further support predictive applications, for example by contributing to the development of regional projections within global species distribution modelling pipelines.

3.2.2. Thematic Services #2 : Extreme Events

Users reported that access to TS#2 was easy and straightforward. They also highlighted that the user toolbox was intuitive and user-friendly, making it simple to select both the area of interest and the relevant extreme event for analysis.

A manifestation of interest about this Thematic Service was expressed by the audience of a presentation of the poster about VLab 1 at the EGU2026 meeting (Vienna, May 2026). Informal discussions with colleagues from marine geology at *Instituto Hidrografico* in Portugal indicate the potential interest in the tools for assessment of impacts on the bottom sedimentary cover and will be explored during the following month.

3.2.3. Thematic Service #3: Gliders

TS#3 was used as a collaborative space to access, process, and analyse marine data, with workflows focused on physical and biogeochemical variables including temperature, salinity, and oxygen, drawing on both glider observations and model outputs. The integration of Jupyter Notebooks with data access services was highlighted as a particular strength of the environment. To further enhance the platform, users suggested improvements to API documentation clarity, simplification of authentication workflows, and an increase in available computing resources to better support computationally intensive tasks.

3.3. VLab 2 “Coastal currents from observations” Feedback

Users feedback identified two practical areas for improvement. Users of the drift modelling functionality expressed a need for quick-start recipes to lower the barrier to entry for new users, while those engaging with Kraken the Code team noted that data access speeds were a limiting factor in their workflows.

Feedback gathered through the consultation process was notably positive regarding the scientific relevance and integration potential of the tools. Participants confirmed that the products were closely aligned with their research topics, and identified potential for incorporation into species distribution modelling pipelines as a predictor variable. The broader applicability of the outputs was also recognised, with one respondent noting that the product could be considered for inclusion within the EMODnet Physics product collections.

VLab 2 was also used in the context of a coastal oceanography lecture at the University of Liège. Teaching physical oceanography to students mostly with a biological background confronts them with a lot of new concepts. Being able to use the BlueCloud virtual research environment allowed the lecturer to focus more on the content of the lecture instead of debugging installation issues that invariably arise when teaching to a larger group of students. All students were able to complete the assignment during the allocated time.

3.4. VLab 3 “Carbon-Plankton Dynamics” Feedback

Feedback collected across the hackathons, consultation sessions, and partner review activities highlighted both the strong reception of the VLab concept and a number of concrete areas requiring development.

The overall concept of a shared VLab environment for exchanging models and results was very well received by participants. However, reviewers noted that the specific purpose and target audience of this particular VLab need to be more clearly defined, so the Jupyter Notebook was adapted accordingly. It was suggested that notebooks should strike a balance between readability *i.e.* exposing simpler routines directly within the notebook while importing only more complex functions from external modules, and transparency, ensuring that users retain full visibility and control over the workflow. Clarifying the intended learning outcomes at the outset was recommended as a way to calibrate the level of detail to the audience. The VLab has been updated since then according to the feedback.

The range of expertise among participants, spanning from marine biologists to computer scientists, surfaced two distinct usability challenges.

For non-technical users, the Vlab was easy to access but the Jupyter environment proved overly complex: error messages were unclear, and without real-time assistance users were frequently unable to proceed. Improvements to error handling were recommended, including more informative and user-friendly messages, as well as the suppression of non-critical warnings that risk disrupting the workflow unnecessarily. These were all changed accordingly in the notebook, and later feedback proved that it was easier to use after modifications.

For experienced modellers, the tool was considered insufficiently flexible, as direct access to model scripts and calibration routines was not available, limiting the ability to modify or explore the underlying NPDZ model. An additional barrier was noted by partners unfamiliar with the R programming language, reinforcing feedback received more broadly that the oceanographic community works predominantly in Python.

Several specific technical issues were identified. The input data loading cell proved difficult to use, with typing errors requiring users to restart the process from scratch; replacing interactive input boxes with editable code cells was proposed as a more stable and transparent alternative. Instructions around input file requirements were insufficiently clear, particularly for users who had not themselves prepared the input data. North Adriatic case study materials, including the associated map and information cells, were either missing or not properly displayed. The absence of progressive cell numbering made it harder for users to follow the workflow and discuss their progress collaboratively. Workspace performance was a significant concern, with file transfers between the general and home workspaces proving extremely slow and providing no progress feedback, creating uncertainty about whether transfers had completed successfully. A number of warnings and error messages appeared throughout the exercise, some non-blocking but nonetheless disorienting, while critical errors related to incorrect input data forced users to restart from earlier steps. Finally, several generated plots were difficult to interpret due to missing legends and insufficient commentary.

Despite these challenges, the visual outputs produced by the exercise were appreciated, and the VLab was identified as potentially valuable for modelling activities in teaching applications. Participants expressed a clear desire to move beyond simply completing the exercise and towards being able to adapt the tool to their own case studies — modifying input data, recalibrating parameters, and running independent simulations. Addressing the documentation, flexibility, and usability gaps identified above would substantially increase the scientific and educational value of the environment.

3.5. VLab 4 “Marine Environmental Indicators” Feedback

Participants engaging with the VLab during the hackathon found the overall interaction experience straightforward and accessible. However, two limitations were identified that constrained the depth of exploration possible within the session. The use of hard-coded coordinates was flagged as an obstacle to usability, as it reduces the flexibility users have to define their own areas of interest and limits the tool's adaptability to different research contexts. Participants also noted that only a narrow subset of data is currently available within the VLab, which restricted the range of analyses that could be carried out during the hackathon.

3.5.1. Ocean Heat Content (OH)

The indicator was identified by consultation respondents as directly relevant to quantifying the impact of climate change, underscoring its scientific value for research communities working on long-term ocean monitoring and environmental assessment. At the technical level, users reported that certain backdoor dependencies made it difficult to re-run specific notebooks, with the Ocean Heat Content notebook within the MEI environment cited as a particular example. Resolving these reproducibility issues would strengthen the reliability of the VLab as a research tool.

3.5.2. Marine Heatwaves (MHW)

Feedback collected points to the scientific and educational relevance of the Marine Heatwaves indicator across two complementary dimensions. Respondents confirmed that the indicator aligns closely with their institutions' research priorities and represents a meaningful contribution to advancing capabilities in support of the European Digital Twin Ocean developments. The VLab was also identified as potentially valuable for modelling activities in teaching applications, suggesting its utility extends beyond purely research-oriented contexts and into capacity building and training environments.

3.5.3. Trophic index (TRIX)

Feedback confirmed that the Trophic Index is well aligned with participating institutions' research priorities, and was recognised as contributing to the monitoring of biodiversity.

3.5.4. Enhanced Storm Severity Index V2 (SSI V2)

Feedback confirmed that the Enhanced Storm Severity Index V2 is well aligned with participating institutions' research priorities, and was recognised as contributing to the improvement of capabilities in support of Digital Twin Ocean developments. This positions the indicator as a relevant tool within the broader European effort to build more robust and integrated ocean monitoring and forecasting infrastructures.

3.6. VLab 5 “Global Fisheries Atlas” Feedback

Feedback gathered from hackathon participants, platform users, and consultation respondents reflects a broadly positive assessment of the Global Fisheries Atlas VLab, with several targeted recommendations for improved clarity and navigation.

Hackathon teams found particular value in the combination of biological and environmental data made possible through the Ecosystem Workbench and Fisheries Atlas, noting that clear documentation and tutorials accelerated their experimentation considerably. The VLab was recognised as a valuable repository uniting fisheries catch data from across the world, and participants confirmed they were able to successfully extract the data they needed for their workflows. The scientific rigour underpinning the applications and data generation processes was also commended.

The primary area of concern raised by multiple participants related to navigational clarity. Several users expressed confusion about the distinction between the Tuna Atlas and the Fisheries Atlas, noting that clicking the Global Fisheries Atlas entry on the Blue-Cloud website directs users to the Tuna Atlas rather than the Fisheries Atlas itself. It was suggested that listing the Fisheries Atlas directly on the Blue-Cloud website would resolve this ambiguity. More broadly, some users noted a lack of clarity around the concepts of a workbench and a VLab, and one team flagged that key navigational elements within the Fisheries Atlas were not sufficiently prominent.

From a technical standpoint, the VLab was commended for several features that support diverse user profiles. The Swagger page for GRSF API testing provides an interactive interface enabling developers and analysts to explore API endpoints without writing code. The Shiny application offers a user-friendly dashboard suited to non-technical users seeking quick data analysis and visualisation. Jupyter Notebook support enables reproducible, documented workflows for more advanced users, and the fully open-source nature of the platform was highlighted as a significant asset for collaborative research, transparency, and community-driven customisation.

Consultation respondents underlined the broader scientific value of the VLab, describing it as useful across many fields of marine biology given the persistent difficulty in locating standardised fisheries datasets. Recommendations included the ongoing maintenance and updating of global fisheries datasets alongside the code used to generate them and the Shiny applications used to explore them. The VLab was also identified as a potential source of predictor variables for future joint species distribution modelling pipelines, pointing to its relevance beyond its immediate use case.

4. Applications

This section documents the practical applications of the Blue-Cloud 2026 Virtual Labs, illustrating how each VLab has been deployed or could be adopted by external users across research, education, and policy contexts. The examples presented demonstrate the VLabs' capacity to support reproducible scientific workflows, lower the technical barriers to advanced marine data analysis, and extend the reach of Blue-Cloud services to diverse user communities, including researchers, educators, and decision-makers. Together, they evidence the added value of the VLab infrastructure in facilitating data-driven insights and collaborative science in support of marine environmental monitoring, fisheries management, and ocean literacy.

4.1 VLab 1 “Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe” applications

VLab 1 can support the monitoring of invasive macroalgae spread in coastal and transboundary marine areas, as demonstrated during the Blue-Cloud 2026 Hackathon held in September 2025. One of the winning teams, “RugOBSS”, used Thematic Service 1, “Transboundary Processes”, which enables access to and analysis of coastal observation data from JERICO-RI and other European research infrastructures. The team combined this capability with VLab 2 to integrate reliable gridded current maps, supporting a more comprehensive assessment of macroalgae dispersion pathways and potential spread dynamics. Full presentation of the use case can be found [here](#).

4.2 VLab 2 “Coastal currents from observations” applications

The VLab 2 has been used at the University of Liège during the lecture of Coastal Oceanography for Master students. They used the VLab to [analyse surface current of the Bay of Calvi](#) (Corsica, France).

In the past, they had to preinstall software for the students at the computer room. Unfortunately, the interaction of the students with the software and tools was rather minimal and occurred mostly only during the lecture. The other option was to install the software on the students laptop, but the diversity of operating systems, OS versions and available resources (disk space and RAM) made this approach time consuming and quite brittle.

A virtual research lab, with all preconfigured software available via a web interface, simplified the teaching significantly. Students only need a web browser and they can connect to VLab 2 via the Blue-Cloud infrastructure using their university credentials. The provided jupyter notebook environment is very versatile as the users can easily install additional software and extend the original scope of the VLab if they want to experiment.

The WITOIL for Blue-Cloud deployed together with the course in Ocean Teacher Global Academy (OTGA) allows the usage of an oil spill modeling application without previous knowledge. The approach to reduce the complexity allows the application to bring more users that would not be willing to use due to code complexity.

4.3 VLab 3 “Carbon-Plankton Dynamics” applications

The VLab also has potential for use in higher education and capacity-building activities, including as part of a course at Ghent University. In this context, it could support hands-on training by allowing students to work directly with marine environmental indicators, data workflows, and visualisation tools in a practical learning environment.

A further concrete application is the deployment of the VLab as a training component on EDITO, demonstrating interoperability between platforms. This allows users to explore how VLab workflows can be integrated with broader European Digital Twin Ocean environments, supporting both technical training and the wider uptake of reusable, interoperable marine data services.

4.4 VLab 4 “Marine Environmental Indicators” applications

The VLab provides two complementary pathways for external users to monitor and assess marine environmental conditions.

The first pathway offers simplified access through a web application, designed for users who require a streamlined, code-free experience. Through a graphical interface, users can generate indicator outputs such as Ocean Heat Content, TRIX, Marine Heatwaves, or SSI v2 by defining a set of input parameters. The system then automatically manages the more complex data extraction, processing, and transformation steps.

The second pathway supports advanced customisation through Jupyter Notebooks, providing the technical flexibility required for more in-depth scientific analysis. Users can directly adapt the underlying code to refine methodologies, for example by modifying detection thresholds and temporal windows for Marine Heatwaves, or by adjusting climatological reference periods.

Outputs generated through either the web application or the notebooks can be saved as interactive visualisations or as NetCDF files for further analysis and reuse.

The MEI VLab acts as a bridge between complex marine datasets and actionable insights for a broad range of stakeholders. It can be used by policymakers, journalists, researchers, and other users with varying levels of technical expertise to produce analyses, reports, and dissemination materials.

A practical example of its use was demonstrated by “Kraken the Code”, one of the winning teams of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon. The team used the VLab to identify environmental conditions associated with octopus boom events in the North Sea and to develop a platform where ideas and analytical workflows can be investigated, refined, and shared with the wider community through D4Science.

4.5 VLab 5 “Global Fisheries Atlas” applications

Regarding the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) part, the knowledge base with its SPARQL endpoint and the programmatic API has primarily been employed with training, tutorial, and demonstration activities through online courses such as OTGA. These activities validated the usability of the services for semantic querying, interoperable data access, and reproducible analytical workflows. In addition to training, it has been exploited as a staging and experimentation environment supporting the continuous evolution of the GRSF, by facilitating the testing and validation of semantic model extensions, data integration workflows, and query adaptations prior to their deployment into the production environment.

With regards to Global Tuna Atlas, FAO is using part of the elaborated data products to populate the FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas and the FAO [fisheries data catalog](#). The various datasets of this atlas are also key to address multiple research topics. Tuna fisheries data are indeed the main source of Essential biological Ocean Variables to study marine species distribution in the upper trophic levels in the high seas at a global scale. Beyond the main tuna species targeted by the fishing vessels, these datasets also report catches for more than 65 species (including billfish, sharks and other taxa). In the past years, the VLab team has been contacted by multiple scientists and research projects that are using these data for modelling open ocean pelagic ecosystems in the global ocean (*e.g.*, for APECOSM or SEAPODYM models data inputs and calibration), to assess the global catches of sharks, to assess the fishing effort from AIS (*e.g.*, Global Fishing Watch).

Beyond the access to the different data products, the VLab is also used to ensure the reproducibility of the work within RStudio which is instrumental for both yearly updates and data quality controls. In addition, end-users products like Shiny apps have been deployed to fit the needs of a wider audience (general public, decision-makers, scientists, etc.). Recently, the VLab team also used the VLab services to deploy a Shiny app for an external project related to tuna fisheries (MANFAD project working on the impact of Fish Aggregating Devices).

Moreover, the VLab resources provide the foundational capabilities for a broad range of future applications, including fisheries monitoring and assessment workflows, FAIR-compliant semantic integration of heterogeneous marine datasets, and others.

5. Conclusion

This deliverable marks the culmination of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project's efforts to design, develop, and refine a portfolio of Virtual Laboratories for marine science. Across five thematic domains i.e. coastal observation, surface current mapping, carbon-plankton modelling, marine environmental indicators, and global fisheries, the project has demonstrated that cloud-based, pre-configured research environments can meaningfully lower the barriers to advanced ocean data analysis and foster collaborative, reproducible science.

The VLabs have moved well beyond proof-of-concept. They have been used in university teaching, applied in hackathon competitions, integrated into monitoring and reporting workflows, and recognised as relevant inputs to EOSC and European Digital Twin Ocean developments. User feedback, gathered through surveys, hackathons, webinars, and open consultations involving hundreds of participants, has confirmed both the value of the infrastructure and the areas where continued investment would have the greatest impact: documentation, data discoverability, collaborative tooling, and computational resource transparency.

As the project concludes, the foundations laid by the Blue-Cloud 2026 VLabs offer a strong platform for continuity. The open-source codebases, DOI-assigned datasets, FAIR-compliant workflows, and training materials developed throughout the project are designed to outlast the project itself, supporting the wider marine science community and contributing to the long-term vision of an integrated European ocean data ecosystem. The lessons learned, both technical and community-driven, provide a clear roadmap for future development and for the sustained engagement of the diverse user communities that have formed around these tools.

6. References

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